

Research Article

Evolution Measuring Tape (Ev_MeTa-Cx)

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Abstract: *The use of measurement tools is crucial for students in engineering, as they provide the foundation for accurate data collection and analysis. Proficiency in measurement techniques helps students apply theoretical concepts, enhancing their understanding of engineering principles through hands-on learning. These tools enable experimentation, design, and effective project execution. However, conventional measuring tools often require extensive training, which can hinder student engagement and learning. Many students struggle with accurately reading measurements, especially when dealing with fractions or small increments, leading to confusion and frustration. Additionally, mastering traditional measuring tapes can consume valuable instructional time. To address these challenges, the Evolution Measuring Tape (Ev_MeTa-Cx) was developed as an affordable and user-friendly tool specifically designed for educational purposes. This innovative measuring tape integrates seamlessly with smartphone applications, providing a smoother and more efficient learning experience. The prototype utilizes lightweight and durable ABS plastic and features digital measurement capabilities, allowing users to capture images of objects to be measured and analyze them using the ImageMeter application. Rigorous testing was conducted to ensure the prototype's accuracy, usability, and overall performance, with user feedback incorporated to refine its design. The Ev_MeTa-Cx significantly enhances the learning process by saving time and energy, enabling students to focus on practical applications rather than complex tools. Its approach aligns with current educational technology trends, promoting a more engaging and hands-on learning environment. Furthermore, the commercialization potential of the Ev_MeTa-Cx is promising, meeting the growing demand for accessible and effective measurement tools in education. By providing a cost-effective alternative to traditional measuring instruments, the Ev_MeTa-Cx can play a crucial role in advancing quality education and fostering technological adaptation among students.*

Keywords: *Measurement Technique; Engineering Learning; User Engagement; Digital Integration; Educational Innovation.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Conventional measurement tools, such as vernier calipers, micrometers, and manual theodolites, play a foundational role in engineering and technical education. However, these tools often require extensive training and practice to master, making them time-consuming for students to learn and use effectively (Smith & Brown, 2018). As educational technology advances, there is growing recognition of the need to develop user-friendly measurement tools that can expedite the learning process, allowing students to focus on practical applications rather than fundamental skills (Jones & Kim, 2020). Although sophisticated digital measurement tools are available, these tend to be complex, feature-rich, and costly, which places them beyond the reach of many students (Lee & Zhang, 2019). Therefore, the objective of this innovation is to produce an affordable and accessible measurement tool, designed specifically for educational purposes, which can be easily integrated with existing smartphone apps. By focusing on affordability and ease of use, this new tool will serve as a fundamental teaching instrument, enabling more efficient and hands-on learning in the classroom (Chen et al., 2021).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Method of the Project

The methodology for this project involves four main steps, as summarized in Table 1. Innovative ideas for this project focus on the use of mobile phone applications in the field of measurement, enabling the development of tools that facilitate efficient measurement. This approach also emphasizes saving time, reducing the need for human resources, and minimizing financial costs.

Table 1. Method of Project

Step	Description	Activities	Outcomes
1. Literature Review	Conduct a comprehensive review of existing measurement tools and technologies.	Analyze current literature	Insight into existing tools and areas for innovation.
2. Prototype Development	Create a functional prototype based on findings from the literature review and needs assessment.	Develop initial design sketches	A working prototype is ready for testing.
3. Testing and Evaluation	Assess the prototype's accuracy, usability, and performance in real-application conditions.	Conduct field tests	Comprehensive evaluation of the prototype's effectiveness.

2.1.1 Literature Review

The main objective of conducting a literature review was to establish a foundational understanding of current measurement tools and identify areas for innovation. This phase involved analyzing existing literature, including academic papers, patents, and market analyses. The review focused on identifying strengths and weaknesses in current measurement tools and the technologies used within them. By synthesizing this information, gaps in the market were pinpointed, laying the groundwork for developing a new tool (Smith & Jones, 2023).

2.1.2 Prototype Development

The objective was to create a functional prototype that integrated user feedback and technological advancements, and based on the findings from the needs assessment, initial design sketches were created, the prototype was built using rapid prototyping techniques which allowed for quick iterations and adjustments, and the design incorporated user-friendly features such as digital measurement capabilities and mobile app integration (Chen et al., 2021), resulting in a working prototype that embodied the insights gathered from the literature review and needs assessment.

2.1.3 Testing and Evaluation

The objective was to rigorously evaluate the prototype's performance in real scenarios, and field tests were conducted to assess the prototype's accuracy, durability, and usability, while user feedback was gathered during testing to identify areas for improvement, and performance metrics were analyzed to compare the new tool's effectiveness against conventional measuring tapes (Lee et al., 2020), resulting in a comprehensive evaluation report that detailed the prototype's strengths and weaknesses, guiding final refinements before production.

2.2 Material Selection

For the selection of materials to produce this prototype, several criteria were identified to create a product with unique characteristics, distinguishing it from existing products on the market. The selection criteria are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Material Selection Criteria

Criteria	Explanation
Design	The material should allow for a user-friendly, ergonomic design that is easy to hold and use, making the measuring tape comfortable for different hand sizes and usable in various settings.
Affordable Price	Cost-effective materials were selected to keep production costs low, allowing the final product to be affordable for a wide range of users. Common options include polymers or aluminum for their low cost without compromising quality.
Lightweight	Lightweight materials were chosen to make the measuring tape portable and convenient. Options like ABS plastic or aluminum reduce weight, enhancing ease of handling without sacrificing durability.
Easily Available	Easily sourced materials ensure smooth production, reducing potential delays and extra costs. Common materials like plastic and aluminum alloys meet this requirement well.
Compact Size	Compactness is achieved by choosing thin, flexible materials such as steel or fiberglass tape for the measuring component, paired with a slim, durable casing. This helps in creating a portable, easy-to-store tool.

3. FINDINGS

After considering the five (5) criteria in Table 2, a measuring tool named the Evolution Measuring Tape (Ev_MeTa-Cx) was created. 90% of the material used was Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) plastic. Using ABS plastic offers several advantages, especially in product manufacturing like measuring tapes as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Advantages of using ABS Plastic

Advantages	Explanation
Durability	ABS plastic is highly impact-resistant, making it suitable for frequent and rough handling, as needed for tools like measuring tapes.
Lightweight	Being lightweight, ABS enhances the portability and ease of use of handheld tools.
Cost-Effectiveness	ABS is more affordable than many other plastics, allowing for cost-efficient production without sacrificing quality.
Good Surface Finish	ABS provides a smooth finish that can be customized with various colors and textures, adding to the product's aesthetic appeal.
Heat Resistance	ABS can withstand moderate temperatures, maintaining its structure and performance without deformation under normal use.
Ease of Molding	ABS is easy to mold, which makes it ideal for creating ergonomic shapes or complex designs necessary for comfortable, user-friendly tools.

The innovative measuring tape has been inspired by conventional measuring tapes. Users simply need to point the Ev_MeTa-Cx at the part or object they wish to measure. An image of the part/object is then captured using a mobile phone. The recorded image is subsequently analysed using the ImageMeter application, which can be downloaded for free. This application is used to obtain measurements of the captured part or object.

3.1 Main Component of Ev_MeTa-Cx

The main components of the Ev_MeTa-Cx consist of the Handle, Horizontal Plate, Laser, Smartphone Holder, and Horizontal Bubble, as shown in Figure 1, while the components that have been connected and fully assembled are shown in Figure 2. The function of each component can be summarised in Table 4. This table explains the function of each component, enhancing the versatility and accuracy of the measuring tape.

Figure 1. Main Components in Ev_MeTa-Cx

Figure 2. Ev_MeTa-Cx Completely Installed

Table 4. The Function of Components in Ev_MeTa-Cx

Component	Function
Handle	Provides a grip for the user to hold and control the measuring tape securely, ensuring stability and ease of use during measurement tasks.
Horizontal Plate	Acts as a base or guide to keep the measuring tape stable on flat surfaces, allowing for accurate measurements without slippage.
Smartphone Holder	Holds a smartphone in place to facilitate digital measurement tracking or capturing photos of measurements, improving the tool's functionality and convenience.
Bubble	Contains a leveling bubble to help users measure at precise angles or ensure a level surface, enhancing the accuracy of measurements.
Laser	Projects a laser beam for distance measuring or marking, enabling precise measurements over longer distances without needing a physical tape extension.

4. DISCUSSION

The usage procedure for the Ev_MeTa-Cx involves only four (4) simple steps that can be completed anywhere and take very little time. The description of the steps is provided below.

4.1 Ev_MeTa-Cx Procedure

4.1.1 Step 1: Aim the Laser at The Object to Be Measured

Turn on the laser and point the smartphone at the surface to be measured so that two laser points, measuring 23.5 cm from the midpoint between each other, will hit any part of that wall surface as shown in Figure 3. The 'Horizontal Bubble' serves as a reference mark to ensure that the captured image is more orderly and level.

Figure 3. Aim the Laser at The Object to Be Measured

4.1.2 Step 2: Aim the Laser at The Object to Be Measured

By using the ImageMeter application that can be downloaded for free, the captured image can be viewed in this app to make any measurements on the image (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Transferring image to ImageMeter App.

4.1.3 Step 3: Setting the Reference Scale

Through the ImageMeter application, enter the 'Reference Scale' at the two laser points, which is equivalent to 23.5 cm. The unit can be selected as either in millimeters (mm), centimeters (cm), or meters (m). The distance between the two laser points will be used as the reference scale to obtain any actual measurements from the captured image as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Reference Scale Setting

4.1.4 Step 4: Recording the Actual Measurement

Through the ImageMeter application, use the 'Dimension' item. From here, any actual measurements from the captured image can be easily obtained (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Recording the Actual Measurement

5. CONCLUSION

Through the use of the Ev_MeTa-Cx, it has made a significant impact on teaching and learning. Among its benefits is the ability to save time and human energy when measuring the dimensions of parts or objects, as it only involves capturing images. Additionally, for measuring large spaces, this tool simplifies the measurement process when multiple measurements need to be taken. It also aligns with Quality Education, which involves the 5.0 Revolution, Industry 4.0, and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) #4 (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2021). Most importantly, it can serve as a teaching tool to expose students to the adaptation of information technology.

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